

Host Diversity of the Parasitic Genus *Cuscuta* sps in District Samba, J&K, India

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Abstract

During the survey conducted in 2023-2024, 22 genera belong to 15 families have been recorded as a host plants of *Cuscuta*. viz. *Murraya paniculata*, *Ficus carica*, *Justicia adhatoda*, *Carrisa spinarium*, *Mallotus philippensis*, *Trifolium alexandrium*, *Xanthium strumarium*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Vitex negundo*, *Mangifera indica*, *Cascabele thevetia*, *Vachellia nilotica*, *Ricinus communis*, *Cassia fistula*, *Flacourtia indica*, *Acacia modesta*, *Cannabis sativa*, *Solanum Lycopersicum*, *Macrotyloma uniflorum*, *Gossyphium sp*, *Duranta sp*, and *Artimesia sp*. Some of host plants representing are herbs, shrubs and trees. It was also observed that plants viz. *Murraya paniculata*, *Ficus carica*, *Justicia adhatoda*, *Mallotus philippensis*, *Trifolium alexandrium*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Vitex negundo*, *Cascabele thevetia*, *Vachellia nilotica*, *Ricinus communis*, *Cassia fistula*, *Flacourtia indica*, *Acacia modesta*, *Duranta sp*, and *Artimesia sp* showed high growth of *Cuscuta* followed by *Carrisa spinarium*, *Xanthium strumarium*, *Cannabis sativa*, *Solanum Lycopersicum*, *Macrotyloma uniflorum*, *Gossyphium sp*. The present results clearly indicate that, dodder ranges in severity based on the species of host. In addition, it was also found that some of the host species viz. *Flacourtia indica*, *Trifolium alexandrium*, *Xanthium strumarium*, *Cascabele thevetia*, *Cassia fistula*, *Solanum Lycopersicum*, *Macrotyloma uniflorum*, *Artimesia* and *Duranta sp* with *Cuscuta* infestation are not reported so far.

Keywords

Cuscuta sps., Parasitic, Host Plant, District, Samba, J&K.

Introduction

Plant of the genus *Cuscuta* belong to family Cuscutaceae is an obligate angiospermic holoparasitic climber on other plants, golden yellow, without root and leaves, also called aftimoon, amarbel, akashbel, beggar weed, hell weed, devil's gut, strangle tare, scald weed and dodder (Noureen, et al., 2019). It grows during the rainy season on the same plant every year (Nadkarni, 2010). It has no chlorophyll and cannot make its food by photosynthesis (Kirtikar and Basu, 1981, 1884; Shikha, 2013, Neetu, 2014). It is commonly found in Ceylon, Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan (Raza, et al., 2015; Said, 1969; Nasir and Ali, 1972). It winds around plants and penetrates the host stem through a specialized organ called the haustorium, forming a direct connections to the vascular bundles to obtain water and nutrients from their host plants (Yoshida et al., 2016; Kokla and Melnyk, 2018).

Objective of study

The purpose of this study was to monitor the diversity of host plant with parasitic *Cuscuta* species in the Samba district, J&K. As this plant is known for major destructor of fruit plant, vegetable, ornamental and medicinal plant.

Review of Literature

Cuscuta plants stems is orange-yellow, yellow, or greenish-yellow because they only have a meagre amount of chlorophyll. Studies of various researchers on genomes of *Cuscuta* species indicate that species have lack of some genes needed for efficient photosynthetic activity (Bhellum and Mangotra, 1996; McNeal et al., 2007; Braukmann et al., 2013; Vogel et al., 2018), which can be considered evidence for transitioning from hemiparasites to holoparasites. Therefore, obtaining water and nutrients from their host is the top priority for their survival. Unlike root parasitic plants that mostly depend on haustorium-inducing factors (Yoshida et al., 2016;), the *Cuscuta* haustorium induction is also regulated by environmental signals such as light signals especially in Blue (Furuhashi, et al., 2011, Furuhashi et al., 2021, Pan et al 2022; Yoo and Sinha, 2022). Apart from this, *Cuscuta* plants are under focus since they cause massive agricultural losses. Several species of *Cuscuta* are monitored in many countries' as noxious weed (Holm, et al., 1997) because they parasitize a wide range of important vegetable and fruit crops, and ornamental plants (Lanini and Kogan, 2005). *Cuscuta* growth is researched that it can decrease host nutrient status and lead to reduced stand, canopy, biomass and fruit weight (Musselman, 1987; Lanini, and Kogan, 2005).

It contains some healthy concerned chemicals like phytochemicals like cuscutin, stigmasterol, kaempferol, dulcitol, myricetin, coumarin, campesterol, sitosterol etc (Manish *et al.* 2012; Anis *et al.* 2002, Ramezan *et al.*, 2023), tetrahydrofuran derivatives, and coumarin from stems (Uddin, *et al.* 2007). Its extract also known to possess anti-steroidogenic, antiviral, and anticonvulsant actions (Gupta, *et al.*, 2003). It is also reported as an antioxidant (Gupta and Sharma, 2006), anti-inflammatory (Katiyar *et al.*, 2015), antimicrobial (Shikha, 2013, Pal, 2006, Ara *et al.*, 2020), antispasmodic, hemodynamic (Gilani and Aftab 1992), antihypertensive, muscle relaxant, and cardiotoxic drug (Singh and Garg, 1973). Some species of *Cuscuta* are used as a carminative, anthelmintic, and used to treat liver disorders and fever and cough in folk medicine (Said, 1969). It is also used for itching (Evans, 1980). *C. reflexa* is orally used to treat rheumatism, sexual problems, and diabetes, while its topical formulation is used to treat toothache (Lee *et al.*, 2008; Mahmood *et al.*, 2013). In the Unani system of medicine, it is considered as an anticancer or anti-tumor drug (Miyahara *et al.*, 1996).

The rural people of Chhattisgarh use its juice in jaundice by mixing it with milk (CGMFPEFED, 2015). Its paste is used in the treatment of Gout (CGMFPEFED, 2015). The juice of plant mixed with the juice of *Saccharum officinarum* is used in the treatment of jaundice (Kirtikar and Basu, 1984). The stem is used in the treatment of body pain and itchy skin. Stem is also used in constipation, flatulence, liver complaints and bilious affections. *Cuscuta reflexa* is also applied as a hair growth promoter (Pandit *et al.*, 2008; Chishty *et al.*, 2024). Seeds are said to be tonic, diaphoretic and demulcent and are used to purify the blood. The cold infusion of seeds is given as a depurative and carminatives in pain and stomach ache (Chopra *et al.*, 1956)

Methodology

An extensive field survey was conducted in 2023-24 at district Samba, Jammu and Kashmir. Samples of *Cuscuta* plants were collected in clean polythene bags from different plant and brought in the laboratory for further identification. Identifications were made with help of some expert, existing literature (Hooker 1872-1879; Cookies, 1958) and research paper.

Result and Discussion

During the survey, conducted in 2023-2024 to locate the susceptible host plants of *Cuscuta* in the area of district Samba, Jammu and Kashmir, India, it was observed that 22 genera belong to 15 families have been recorded as a host plants of *Cuscuta* (Table 1). viz. *Murraya paniculata*, *Ficus carica*, *Justicia adhatoda*, *Carrisa spinarium*, *Mallotus philippensis*, *Trifolium alexandrium*, *Xanthium strumarium*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Vitex negundo*, *Mangifera indica*, *Cascabele thevetia*, *Vachellia nilotica*, *Ricinus communis*, *Cassia fistula*, *Flacourtia indica*, *Acacia modesta*, *Cannabis sativa*, *Solanum Lycopersicum*, *Macrotyloma uniflorum*, *Gossyphium sp*, *Duranta sp*, and *Artimesia sp*. Some of host plants representing are herbs, shrubs and trees. Their life span may be annual, biennial or perennial. The present results clearly indicate that, dodder ranges in severity based on the species of host (Kumar *et al.* 2012). It was also observed that plants viz. *Murraya paniculata*, *Ficus carica*, *Justicia adhatoda*, *Mallotus philippensis*, *Trifolium alexandrium*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Vitex negundo*, *Cascabele thevetia*, *Vachellia nilotica*, *Ricinus communis*, *Cassia fistula*, *Flacourtia indica*, *Acacia modesta*, *Duranta sp*, and *Artimesia sp* showed high growth of *Cuscuta* followed by *Carrisa spinarium*, *Xanthium strumarium*, *Cannabis sativa*, *Solanum Lycopersicum*, *Macrotyloma uniflorum*, *Gossyphium sp*. Similar observations were also made by some researcher on *Cuscuta* – host plants (Reddy, *et al.* 1990; Patel *et al.* 2004; Sarina, *et al.* 2008; Kappor, V and Sharma, 2008; Mukhtar *et al.*, 2012; Nikam *et al.* 2014; Patel and Patel, 2010; Preeti *et al.*, 2017). In addition to this, it was also found that some of the host species viz. *Flacourtia indica*, *Trifolium alexandrium*, *Xanthium strumarium*, *Cascabele thevetia*, *Cassia fistula*, *Solanum Lycopersicum*, *Macrotyloma uniflorum*, *Artimesia* and *Duranta sp* with *Cuscuta* infestation are not reported so far.

c. d.
Cuscuta spp. infestation on host plant- a) *Cascabele thevetia* b) *Ficus carica*
c) *Trifolium alexandrinum* d) *Mellotus philippens*

Conclusion

During the survey, conducted in 2023-2024 to locate the susceptible host plants of *Cuscuta* in the area of district Samba, Jammu and Kashmir, India, it was observed that 22 genera belong to 15 families have been recorded as a host plants of *Cuscuta*. In addition to this, it was also found that some of the host species viz. *Flacourtia indica*, *Trifolium alexandrinum*, *Xanthium strumarium*, *Cascabele thevetia* *Cassia fistula*, *Solanum Lycopersicum*, *Macrotyloma uniflorum*, *Artimesia* and *Duranta sp* with *Cuscuta* infestation are not reported so far.

Table 1.:Occurrence of *Cuscuta* sp. on different susceptible host plant

S. No.	Botanical names of host plants	Vernacular names of host plants	Family	Habit	Uses of host plant	Growth on host plant
1	<i>Murraya paniculata</i>	Moraya	Rutaceae	Shrub	Fodder, condemants	High growth
2	<i>Ficus carica</i>	Wild Fig	Moraceae	Tree	Fruit	High growth
3	<i>Justicia adhatoda</i>	Vasaka Adhatoda	Acanthaceae	Shrub	Against insect ,Herbal medicine	High growth
4	<i>Carrisa opaca</i>	Garna karonda	Apocynaceae	Shrub	Fruit, herbal medicine	Moderate growth
5	<i>Mallotus philippensis</i>	Kamala, kumkum tree, Kambel	Euphorbiaceae	Tree	Dye, herbal remedies	High growth
6	<i>Trifolium alexandrium</i>	Baeseem clover	Fabaceae	Herb	Fodder, green manure	High growth
7	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	Cocklebur, woolgarie bur	Asteraceae	Herb	Chinese herbal medicine	Moderate
8	<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i>	Indian jujube, ber	Rhamnaceae	Tree	Fodder, fruit and herbal medicine	High growth
9	<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Chaste tree , Vanna, horseshoe	Laminaceae	Shrub	Against insect, herbal medicine	High growth
10	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Mango, aam	Anacardiaceae	Tree	Fruit	Moderate
11	<i>Cascabele thevetia</i>	Kaner, chilca	Apocynaceae	Shrub	Poisonous plant,	High growth
12	<i>Vachellia nilotica</i>	Babul, kiker	Fabaceae	Tree	Fodder, dye, herbal medicine	High growth
13	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Casterbean, ricin, arandi	Euphorbiaceae	Tree	Oil, herbal medicine	High growth
14	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Ameltash, golden shower	Fabaceae	Tree	Herbal medicine	High growth
15	<i>Flacourtia indica</i>	Kakoa, Indian plum	Salicaceae	Tree	Fodder, Fruit , herbal medicine	High growth
16	<i>Acacia modesta</i>	Phalahi	Fabaceae	Tree	Fodder ,Herbal medicine	High growth
17	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	Hemp, bhang,	Cannabaceae	Herb	Fibre, drugs, herbal medicine	Moderate
18	<i>Solanum Lycopersicum</i>	Tomato	Solanaceae	Herb	Fruit	Moderate
19	<i>Macrotyloma uniflorum</i>	Kulth-pigeonpea, horse gram	Fabaceae	Herb	Seed,herbal , medicine	Moderate
20	<i>Gossyphium</i> sp	Kapas	Malvaceae	Herb	Fodder, cotton	Moderate
21	<i>Duranta</i> sp	Golden hedge	Verbenaceae	Shrub	Ornamental , herbal medicine	High growth
22	<i>Artemisia</i> sp	Chau, sweet sagewort	Asteraceae	Herb	Herbal medicine	High growth

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